

Study of Soil Alkalinity of Mahad Taluka, Raigad District, Maharashtra by Acid Titration Method Using Methyl Orange and Phenolphthalein Indicators

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Abstract:

The present study focuses on the determination of soil alkalinity in Mahad Taluka, Raigad District, Maharashtra, using the acid titration method with phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicators. Soil alkalinity significantly influences soil fertility, nutrient availability, and crop productivity. Soil samples collected from different locations were analyzed using standard hydrochloric acid. Results indicated low to moderate alkalinity dominated by bicarbonate alkalinity. The study points up the need for frequently soil testing for sustainable agricultural management.

Keywords: Soil pH, soil analysis, soil alkalinity, Mahad.

Introduction:

Soil alkalinity refers to the presence of soluble salts such as carbonates, bicarbonates, and hydroxides of sodium, potassium magnesium and calcium. These salts affect soil structure, nutrient intake, and biological activity. Determination of soil alkalinity is essential for proper soil and crop management.

Mahad Taluka it is the part of Konkan region and situated in Raigad District of Maharashtra. The area receives heavy monsoon rainfall in rainy season and is characterized by red soils. Agriculture is the main livelihood, with rice being the dominant primary crop. Rice is the chief and predominant agricultural product in Mahad and the Konkan region as a whole, often covering 60-70% of cultivable land. The Mahad area has soils suitable for rice cultivation, though some land near the coast can be saline Other Major Crops than rice grown during the monsoon season include ragi (nachni) and small millets Vari.

Objectives:

1. To estimate soil alkalinity of Mahad Taluka.
2. To determine carbonate and bicarbonate alkalinity.
3. To apply titration method using suitable indicators.
4. To assess the impact of alkalinity on soil health.

Materials and Methods:

Soil samples were collected from 0–20 cm depth. Five grams of soil were mixed with 100 mL distilled water, shaken thoroughly, and filtered. The extract was titrated against 0.02 N HCl using phenolphthalein and methyl orange indicators.

Principle:

Alkalinity is determined by neutralizing alkaline components with a standard acid. Phenolphthalein indicator indicates hydroxide and carbonate alkalinity, while methyl orange

indicates total alkalinity. This method is widely accepted in India and has been standardized by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research.

Preparation of Soil Extract:

A known weight of soil (10 g) was transferred into a clean conical flask, and 50 mL of distilled water was added. The mixture was shaken thoroughly for 30 minutes and allowed to settle. The clear supernatant was filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper and used for alkalinity estimation.

Experimental Procedure:

An 10 mL of the soil extract was pipette out in a conical flask and to that few drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added. If a pink colour appeared, the solution was titrated with standard hydrochloric acid until the pink colour

just disappeared. The volume of acid consumed was recorded as phenolphthalein alkalinity (P-alkalinity), representing hydroxide and half of the carbonate alkalinity.

Subsequently, If pink colour not appeared then methyl orange indicator was added to the same solution and titration was continued until the colour changed from yellow to orange. The additional volume of acid required was recorded as total alkalinity (M-alkalinity), representing the combined effect of carbonate and bicarbonate alkalinity.

The selection of these two indicators allows differentiation between various alkaline components, as supported by earlier Indian soil studies and ICAR-recommended procedures.

Observation Table: Determination Of Soil Alkalinity

Sr. No.	Sample Location Mahad	Volume of Soil Extract (ml)	Normality of HCl	P-Value (ml)	M-Value (ml)	Remarks
1	Varandh	10	0.02	0.0	3.6	Bicarbonate alkalinity
2	Karanjkhoh	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
3	Kemburli	10	0.02	0.0	4.1	Bicarbonate alkalinity
4	Natondi	10	0.02	0.0	5.5	Bicarbonate alkalinity
5	Birwadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
6	Gandharpale	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	Bicarbonate alkalinity
7	Nadgaon	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	Bicarbonate alkalinity
8	Mangharun	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	Bicarbonate alkalinity
9	Bhogaon	10	0.02	0.0	3.3	Bicarbonate alkalinity
10	Nangalwadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	Bicarbonate alkalinity
11	Pimpaldari	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
12	Pimpaldari	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
13	Sakadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
14	Sawad	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity
15	Ladavali	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	Bicarbonate alkalinity

Calculations:

Alkalinity (mg/L as CaCO₃) = (Volume of acid × Normality × 50,000) / Volume of sample

Given:

- Volume of soil extract = **50 ml**
- Normality of HCl = **0.02 N**
- Volume of acid used (M) = **..... ml**

Sr. No.	Sample Location Mahad	Volume of Soil Extract (ml)	Normality of HCl	P-Value (ml)	M-Value (ml)	Alkalinity mg/L as CaCO ₃
1	Varandh	10	0.02	0.0	3.6	360
2	Karanjkhohol	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
3	Kemburli	10	0.02	0.0	4.1	410
4	Natondi	10	0.02	0.0	5.5	550
5	Birwadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
6	Gandharpale	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	510
7	Nadgaon	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	510
8	Mangharun	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	510
9	Bhogaon	10	0.02	0.0	3.3	330
10	Nangalwadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.1	510
11	Pimpaldari	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
12	Pimpaldari	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
13	Sakadi	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
14	Sawad	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500
15	Ladavali	10	0.02	0.0	5.0	500

Results and Discussion:

The soils of Mahad Taluka showed low to moderate alkalinity. Bicarbonate alkalinity was dominant. Hydroxide alkalinity was absent. This indicates limited alkaline stress in most agricultural fields. Total alkalinity ranged 360–550 mg/L CaCO₃. Majority of soils exhibited bicarbonate-dominated alkalinity, consistent with coastal and irrigated Indian soils [1,2]. Sites with higher P-values indicate presence of carbonate + hydroxide ions, suggesting localized sodicity risk [3]. Comparison with ICAR and CSSRI guidelines shows results are within expected ranges for Western Ghats soils [4,5,6].

Conclusion:

The study concludes that Mahad Taluka soils are mostly non-problematic with respect to alkalinity. Acid titration using indicators is an effective method for soil alkalinity assessment.

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